

Checklist of Cartilaginous Species with Current Status and Conservation Strategies in Turkish Marine Waters

Cemal Turan^{1,2*}

¹Iskenderun Technical University, Faculty of Marine Sciences and Technology, Molecular Ecology and Fisheries Genetics Laboratory, 31220 Iskenderun, Hatay, Türkiye. ²University of Split, Department of Marine Studies, 21000 Split, Croatia. ³Iskenderun Technical University, Maritime Technology Vocational School of Higher Education, Underwater Technologies, 31200 Iskenderun, Hatay, Türkiye.

Research Article

Citation: Turan, C., Uyan, A., Soldo, A., Dođdu, S. A., Ergüden, D. (2025). Checklist of Cartilaginous Species with Current Status and Conservation Strategies in Turkish Marine Waters. *Tethys Env. Sci.* 2(1): 31-61.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15032119

Received: 11 January 2025

Accepted: 05 March 2025

Available Online: 15 March 2025

Publication Date: 17 March 2025

 Copyright

2025 Turan et al.,

Distributed Under

CC-BY 4.0

Abstract

Cartilaginous fishes (Chondrichthyes) have 1282 species of sharks, batoids, and chimaeras worldwide. The class Chondrichthyes comprises 1226 species under the subclass Elasmobranchii and 56 species under the subclass Holocephali. The Mediterranean, particularly known for its rich diversity of cartilaginous species, is expected to suffer the most severe global decline in the number, diversity, and distribution of these species as a result of overfishing, with some species even facing extinction. The Mediterranean ecosystem is home to 89 cartilaginous species, containing 49 sharks, 38 batoids, and 2 chimaeras species. There are a total of 71 cartilaginous fish species in Turkish marine waters, 70 of which are elasmobranchs (38 shark and 32 batoid species) and 1 is a chimaera. Cartilaginous fishes are not the target of commercial fisheries in Türkiye, but are often unintentionally captured as bycatch through trawl, gillnet, and longline fisheries. Based on the IUCN Red List criteria, 27% of cartilaginous species are categorized as Vulnerable (VU), 26% as Endangered (EN), and 16% as Critically Endangered (CR) in Turkish marine waters. The remaining species are classified as follows: 14% as Near Threatened (NT), 13% as Least Concern (LC), and 4% as Data Deficient (DD). Numerous studies have been conducted in Turkish marine waters on the bio-ecology of cartilaginous species to support regulations to improve their conservation; however, genetic studies remain quite limited.

Keywords: *Elasmobranchs, conservation, bio-ecology, genetics, Turkish marine waters.*

Introduction

Cartilaginous fishes (Chondrichthyes) are jawed fish with skeletons consisting mainly of cartilage and have 1282 sharks, batoids (rays and skates), and chimaeras species worldwide, including 1226 species of the subclass Elasmobranchii (537 species of sharks in 34 families and 689 species of batoids in 20 families) and 56 chimaeras species of subclass Holocephali in 3 families (Nelson et al., 2016). Although cartilaginous species are prevalent in marine ecosystems and some are even found in freshwater habitats, the classification of these fishes remains ambiguous and is a subject of cogitating over for many species and genera (Ebert and Stehmann, 2013; Ebert et al., 2013; UNEP/MAP SPA/RAC, 2018). In particular, the Mediterranean is predominantly prone to unsteadiness in the taxonomic classification of cartilaginous species, largely due to the range of its basins and sub-basins (Iglesias, 2014). Negotiations have persisted regarding the presence of cartilaginous fish in these basins and the fluctuations in their abundance.

Cartilaginous fish, an evolutionarily conservative group of organisms, have been able to survive successfully in aquatic ecosystems for over 400 million years. Despite their survival and evolutionary stability, they are increasingly at risk of extinction due to strong fisheries pressure (direct or indirect). Since cartilaginous fishes can be found in similar habitats as target fish species, they are caught as bycatch during commercial fisheries and discarded due to their low or no commercial value (Cavanagh and Gibson, 2007). Evidence suggests that cartilaginous fish in the Mediterranean are declining in abundance, diversity, and distribution, facing a worse scenario than populations worldwide (Walker et al., 2005). These declines can be attributed to several factors, such as the semi-enclosed nature of the Mediterranean and intensive fisheries activities in coastal and pelagic waters, marine pollution, the degradation of vital nursery grounds and other important coastal habitats, uncontrolled coastal urbanization and unplanned human intervention as well as the *K*-selected life history characteristics of cartilaginous fishes (Cailliet et al., 2005; Kabasakal, 2021). Particularly, the reduction in species richness of the eastern basin caused by overfishing, leading to depletion and potentially even extinction of native cartilaginous species, has been compensated by the introduction of new Indo-Pacific origin species via the Suez Canal (Zenetos et al., 2010; Ferretti et al., 2013; Turan et al., 2018).

According to FAO's official fishery and aquaculture statistics, from 1950 to 2009, the peak landings of sharks and rays in the Mediterranean reached 16007 tons in 1988 and 498 tons in 2009, respectively. Furthermore, between 2010 and 2022, the highest recorded landing of sharks occurred in 2015, totalling 824 tons, while the peak landing for rays was in 2019, totalling 1710 tons. Chimaeras were captured in minimal quantities and their landings were recorded only in 2020, 2021, and 2022 as 0.07, 0.17, and 0.15 tons, respectively (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Landings of cartilaginous fishes in the Mediterranean during 2010-2022 (FAO, 2024).

In Turkish marine waters, cartilaginous fishes are also not the target of commercial fisheries and are often unintentionally captured as bycatch through trawl, gill-net, and longline fisheries (Turan and Ergüden, 2012; Yağlıoğlu et al., 2015; Ergüden et al., 2022). Additionally, larger species are frequently caught by purse-seine nets along the Turkish coasts (Başusta et al., 2016). Fisheries statistics of the Turkish Statistical Institute (TURKSTAT), categorizing “sharks”, “rays” and “angel sharks” within elasmobranchs between 2000 and 2023 indicate that the highest shark landing was recorded as 2880 tons in 2000, while the lowest decrease dramatically to 1.4 tons in 2023. The highest ray landing was recorded at 1100 tons in 2000, while the lowest dropped sharply to 0.7 tons in 2021. Angel sharks, caught in smaller quantities compared to sharks and rays, reached their peak landing of 60 tons in 2000, while their bottom amount declined to 0.2 tons in 2020 (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Landings of elasmobranchs in Turkish marine waters during 2000-2023 (TURKSTAT, 2024).

Elasmobranchs have been captured commercially in Türkiye since the 1990s and their consumption is very limited due to public taste preferences. However, their by-products and bioactive compounds hold substantial economic potential globally (Vennila et al., 2011; Fuoichi et al., 2017; Seixas et al., 2020; Uyan et al., 2020a, 2021; Bak et al., 2022; Agustin et al., 2023; Aydođdu et al., 2023; Coscueta et al., 2024; Lamas and Massa, 2024). Extracts rich in collagen and glucosamine from shark cartilage, especially, are used in health supplements and cosmetics (Merly and Smith, 2015; Isaacs and Hellberg, 2021; Li et al., 2022; Lu et al., 2022), and in wound healings (Musick, 2005; Tanna et al., 2020). Chondroitin sulphate ($C_{13}H_{21}NO_{15}S$) derived from shark cartilage is also a therapeutic used to relieve symptoms of osteoarthritis and other joint conditions (Volpi, 2009; Vazquez et al., 2013, 2020; Irianto, 2022; Brito et al., 2023). Shark liver oil, renowned for vitamins A and D, as well as omega-3 fatty acids, is popular as a nutritional supplement (Hole and Taylor, 1996; Turan et al., 2007; Venugopal et al., 2016; Yıđın et al., 2019; Amri et al., 2021). Shark skin is used as a useful ingredient for the production and consumption of various leather products (Fofandi et al., 2020). Cartilaginous fish encounter anthropogenic threats owing to both being caught as bycatch and the intensive use of their by-products industrially, and therefore the need for effective conservation strategies is essential for their sustainability.

Research into their bio-ecological parameters and genetic diversity is essential for comprehending and protecting the health of marine ecosystems. Numerous studies, primarily on length-weight relationships, have been conducted to determine the bio-ecological characteristics of cartilaginous species in Turkish marine waters and to aid legal regulations; however, genetic studies have been quite scarce. Therefore, this review focuses on evaluating the list and current status and also possible conservation strategies from a bio-ecological and genetic perspective for cartilaginous fishes in Turkish marine waters.

Biodiversity and IUCN Status of Cartilaginous Fishes in Mediterranean Coasts of Türkiye

Located at the junction of three continents, Europe, Africa, and Asia, the Mediterranean connects to the Atlantic Ocean via the Strait of Gibraltar in the west, to the Red Sea *via* the Suez Canal in the southeast, and to the Black Sea through the Turkish Straits System consisting of the Dardanelles, the Sea of Marmara and the Bosphorus in the northeast (Ođuz et al., 1993). The Mediterranean is recognized as a biodiversity hotspot because of its diverse ecosystems, including coastal reefs, sea meadows, sandy bays, deep-sea coral communities, hydrothermal vents, muddy plains, and steep slopes (Danovaro et al., 2010). While it is noted for its Chondrichthyes-rich ecosystem, the Mediterranean also harbours the most endangered cartilaginous species compared to other seas worldwide (Dulvy et al., 2016). Serena et al. (2020) reported a total of 88 cartilaginous species in the latest cartilaginous checklist of the Mediterranean (including the Black Sea). However, Turan et al. (2021) reported whale shark *Rhincodon typus* off the Samandađ coast of Türkiye in the Northeastern Mediterranean and it was included in the Mediterranean and Turkish cartilaginous fish fauna inventory (Turan et al., 2024a). Turan et al. (2024b) reported the blonde ray *Raja brachyura* for the first time from Turkish marine waters that a female specimen was captured during a trawling survey on 17 March 2019 in Antalya Bay, north-eastern Mediterranean, making it the 14th Rajid species for Turkish marine ichthyofauna to date.

Thus, currently the Mediterranean is home to a total of 89 species of cartilaginous species, including 49 sharks, 38 batoids and 2 chimeras (1 of which is questionable) species. No less than 53% of cartilaginous species in the Mediterranean are classified as Vulnerable (VU), Endangered (EN) and Critically Endangered (CR), while a large proportion (20%) are still in the category of Data Deficient (DD) by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) (Dulvy et al., 2014; Otero et al., 2019; Serena et al., 2020).

Up to date, cartilaginous fish taxa in Turkish marine waters were represented by a total of 71 species, comprising 70 species of Elasmobranchii (sharks and batoids) and 1 species of Holocephali (chimaera). Among elasmobranchs, sharks are represented by 38 species belonging to 19 families, and batoids by 32 species belonging to 10 families. The most dominant shark family in terms of species diversity on Turkish coasts is Carcharhinidae (9 species), followed by the families Triakidae (4 species), Squatinidae (3 species), Lamnidae (3 species), Hexanchidae (2 species), Squalidae (2 species), Alopiidae (2 species), Scyliorhinidae (2 species). The remaining families Echinorhinidae, Centrophoridae, Etmopteridae, Somniosidae, Oxynotidae, Dalatiidae, Rhincodontidae, Odontaspidae, Cetorhinidae, Pentanchidae, and Sphyrnidae are each represented by 1 species. Among batoids in Turkish marine waters, the family with the most species diversity is the Rajidae (14 species), followed by Dasyatidae (8 species), and Torpedinidae (3 species). The remaining families Rhinobatidae, Glaucostegidae, Gymnuridae, Aetobatidae, Myliobatidae, Rhinopteridae, and Mobulidae are each represented by 1 species. The current checklist showing the cartilaginous species distributed in Turkish marine waters and their IUCN status is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. The checklist of cartilaginous fishes in Turkish marine waters, including their IUCN status (CR, Critically Endangered; EN, Endangered; VU, Vulnerable; NT, Near Threatened; LC, Least Concern; DD, Data Deficient) and distributions.

Family/Species	Common Name	IUCN Status	Distribution
Family Hexanchidae			
<i>Hepranchias perlo</i> (Bonnaterre, 1788)	Sharpnose seven-gill shark	DD	MS, AS
<i>Hexanchus griseus</i> (Bonnaterre, 1788)	Bluntnose six-gill shark	NT	MS, AS, SM, BS
Family Echinorhinidae			
<i>Echinorhinus brucus</i> (Bonnaterre, 1788)	Bramble shark	EN	MS, AS, SM
Family Squalidae			
<i>Squalus acanthias</i> Linnaeus, 1758*	Spotted spiny dogfish	EN	MS, AS, SM, BS
<i>Squalus blainville</i> (Risso, 1827)*	Longnose spurdog	DD	MS, AS, SM, BS
Family Centrophoridae			
<i>Centrophorus uyato</i> (Rafinesque, 1810)	Little gulper shark	EN	MS, AS, SM
Family Etmopteridae			
<i>Etmopterus spinax</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Velvet belly	VU	MS, AS
Family Somniosidae			
<i>Somniosus rostratus</i> (Risso, 1827)	Little sleeper shark	LC	MS, AS
Family Oxynotidae			
<i>Oxynotus centrina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)*	Angular rough shark	EN	MS, AS, SM, BS
Family Dalatiidae			
<i>Dalatias licha</i> (Bonnaterre, 1788)	Kitefin shark	VU	MS, AS, SM

Family Squatinidae

<i>Squatina aculeata</i> Cuvier, 1829*	Sawback angelshark	CR	MS, AS
<i>Squatina oculata</i> Bonaparte, 1840*	Smoothback angelshark	CR	MS, AS, SM
<i>Squatina squatina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)*	Angelshark	CR	MS, AS, SM, BS

Family Rhincodontidae

<i>Rhincodon typus</i> Smith, 1828	Whale shark	EN	MS
------------------------------------	-------------	----	----

Family Odontaspidae

<i>Odontaspis ferox</i> (Risso, 1810)	Smalltooth sand tiger	EN	MS, AS
---------------------------------------	-----------------------	----	--------

Family Alopiidae

<i>Alopias superciliosus</i> Lowe, 1841*	Bigeye thresher	VU	MS, AS, SM
<i>Alopias vulpinus</i> (Bonnaterre, 1788)*	Thresher shark	VU	MS, AS, SM, BS

Family Cetorhinidae

<i>Cetorhinus maximus</i> (Gunnerus, 1765)*	Basking shark	EN	MS, AS
---	---------------	----	--------

Family Lamnidae

<i>Carcharodon carcharias</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)*	Great white shark	VU	MS, AS, SM
<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i> Rafinesque, 1810*	Shortfin mako	EN	MS, AS
<i>Lamna nasus</i> (Bonnaterre, 1788)*	Porbeagle	VU	MS, AS, SM

Family Pentanchidae

<i>Galeus melastomus</i> Rafinesque, 1810	Blackmouth catshark	LC	MS, AS, SM
---	---------------------	----	------------

Family Scyliorhinidae

<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Smallspotted catshark	LC	MS, AS, SM, BS
<i>Scyliorhinus stellaris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Nursehound	VU	MS, AS, SM

Family Triakidae

<i>Galeorhinus galeus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)*	Tope shark	CR	MS, AS, SM
<i>Mustelus asterias</i> Cloquet, 1819	Starry smoothhound	NT	MS, AS, SM, BS
<i>Mustelus mustelus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Smoothhound	EN	MS, AS, SM, BS
<i>Mustelus punctulatus</i> Risso, 1827	Blackspotted smoothhound	VU	MS, AS, SM

Family Carcharhinidae

<i>Carcharhinus altimus</i> (Springer, 1950)	Bignose shark	NT	MS
<i>Carcharhinus brachyurus</i> (Günther, 1870)	Copper shark	VU	MS
<i>Carcharhinus brevipinna</i> (Valenciennes, 1839)	Spinner shark	VU	MS, AS
<i>Carcharhinus falciformis</i> (Bibron, 1839)*	Silky shark	VU	MS
<i>Carcharhinus limbatus</i> (Valenciennes, 1839)	Blacktip shark	VU	MS
<i>Carcharhinus obscurus</i> (Lesueur, 1818)	Dusky shark	EN	MS
<i>Carcharhinus plumbeus</i> (Nardo, 1827)*	Sandbar shark	EN	MS, AS
<i>Carcharias taurus</i> Rafinesque, 1810	Sandtiger shark	CR	MS, AS
<i>Prionace glauca</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)*	Blue shark	NT	MS, AS

Family Sphyrnidae

<i>Sphyrna zygaena</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)*	Smooth hammerhead	VU	MS, AS
--	-------------------	----	--------

Family Torpedinidae

<i>Tetronarce nobiliana</i> (Bonaparte, 1835)	Electric ray	LC	MS, AS, SM
<i>Torpedo marmorata</i> Risso, 1810	Marbled electric ray	VU	MS, AS, SM
<i>Torpedo torpedo</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Common torpedo	VU	MS, AS, SM

Family Rhinobatidae

Rhinobatos rhinobatos (Linnaeus, 1758)* Common guitarfish CR MS, AS

Family Glaucostegidae

Glaucostegus cemiculus (Geoffroy Saint-Hilaire, 1817)* Blackchin guitarfish CR MS, AS

Family Rajidae

Dipturus batis (Linnaeus, 1758) Blue skate CR MS, AS, SM

Dipturus oxyrinchus (Linnaeus, 1758) Longnosed skate NT MS, AS, SM

Leucoraja circularis (Couch, 1838) Sandy ray EN MS, AS

Leucoraja fullonica (Linnaeus, 1758) Shagreen ray VU MS, AS

Leucoraja naevus (Müller & Henle, 1841) Cuckoo ray LC MS, AS, SM

Raja asterias Delaroche, 1809 Mediterranean starry ray NT MS, AS, SM

Raja brachyura Lafont, 1873 Blonde ray NT MS

Raja clavata Linnaeus, 1758* Thornback ray NT MS, AS, SM, BS

Raja miraletus Linnaeus, 1758 Brown ray LC MS, AS, SM

Raja montagui Fowler, 1910 Spotted ray LC MS, AS, SM

Raja polystigma Regan, 1923 Speckled ray LC AS

Raja radula Delaroche, 1809 Rough ray EN MS, AS, SM

Raja undulata Lacepède, 1802 Undulate ray EN MS, AS

Rostroraja alba (Lacepède, 1803) White skate EN MS, AS

Family Dasyatidae

Bathytoshia lata (Garman, 1880) Brown stingray VU MS, AS

Dasyatis marmorata (Steindachner, 1892) Marbled stingray NT MS

Dasyatis pastinaca (Linnaeus, 1758) Common stingray VU MS, AS, SM, BS

Dasyatis tortonesei Capapé, 1975 Tortonese's stingray DD MS, AS, SM

Himantura leoparda Manjaji-Matsumoto & Last, 2008 Leopard whipray EN MS

Himantura cf uarnak (Gmelin, 1789) Honeycomb stingray EN MS

Pteroplatytrygon violacea (Bonaparte, 1832) Pelagic stingray LC MS, AS

Taeniurops grabatus (Geoffroy St. Hilaire, 1817) Round stingray NT MS

Family Gymnuridae

Gymnura altavela (Linnaeus, 1758) Spiny butterfly ray EN MS, AS, SM, BS

Family Actobatidae

Aetomylaeus bovinus (Geoffroy St. Hilaire, 1817) Bull ray CR MS, AS, SM

Family Myliobatidae

Myliobatis aquila (Linnaeus, 1758) Common eagle ray CR MS, AS, SM

Family Rhinopteridae

Rhinoptera marginata (Geoffroy St. Hilaire, 1817) Lusitanian cownose ray CR MS, AS

Family Mobulidae

Mobula mobular (Bonnaterre, 1788)* Devil fish EN MS, AS

Family Chimaeridae

Chimaera monstrosa Linnaeus, 1758 Rabbit fish VU MS, AS, SM

*, Cartilaginous fish species prohibited from catching along the Turkish coasts; MS, Mediterranean Sea; AS, Aegean Sea; SM, Sea of Marmara; BS, Black Sea.

Table 1 summarizes that in Turkish marine waters, 13 shark, 5 batoid, and 1 chimera species are classified as Vulnerable (VU), 11 shark and 8 batoid species are Endangered (EN), and 5 shark

and 6 batoid species are Critically Endangered (CR). On the other hand, the Communiqué No. 5/1, published in the Official Gazette of the Republic of Türkiye, prohibits the catching of 18 shark species and 5 batoid species (indicated with the asterisks) to legally protect elasmobranch stocks in Turkish marine waters (Official Gazette, 2020). Nevertheless, catching of 1 shark (*Carcharias taurus*) and 4 batoid species (*Dipturus batis*, *Aetomylaeus bovinus*, *Myliobatis aquila*, *Rhinoptera marginata*) classified as CR, and 6 sharks (*Echinorhinus brucus*, *Centrophorus uyato*, *Rhincodon typus*, *Odontaspis ferox*, *Mustelus mustelus*, *Carcharhinus obscurus*) and 7 batoid species (*Leucoraja circularis*, *Raja radula*, *Raja undulata*, *Rostroraja alba*, *Himantura leoparda*, *Himantura uarnak*, *Gymnura altavela*) listed as EN, is not prohibited in Turkish marine waters.

Elasmobranchs are found along the coasts of the Mediterranean, Aegean Sea, Sea of Marmara, and Black Seas in Türkiye; however, chimaeras, represented by only one species, are found in all these seas except the Black Sea. The Mediterranean coast of Türkiye has the greatest diversity of cartilaginous fish, hosting 38 shark species, 31 batoid species and 1 chimera species, followed by the Aegean Sea coast with 31 shark species, 27 batoid species and 1 chimera species. The Sea of Marmara is home to 17 shark species, 16 batoid species and 1 chimera species. The Black Sea coast have the lowest diversity of cartilaginous fish in Türkiye, with 8 shark and 3 batoid species (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Map showing the distribution of cartilaginous fishes according to their numbers in each part of Turkish marine waters.

Bioecological and Genetic Studies of Cartilaginous Fishes in Turkish Coasts

Bioecological studies

To date, the most common type of bio-ecological research conducted on cartilaginous fishes distributed in Turkish marine waters has been length-weight relationship (LWR) and von Bertalanffy growth function (VBGF) parameters studies. To the best of our knowledge, a total of 90 studies about

LWRs on 37 species were identified, 23 studies of which also examined VBGF parameters. At the same time, a total of 3 studies focused solely on VBGF parameters were found for three different species. The complete inventory list summarizing the LWR and VBGF studies of cartilaginous species in Turkish marine waters is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. The inventory list of bio-ecological studies of cartilaginous fishes along the Turkish coasts.

References	Species	N	Sex	LWR parameters		VBGF parameters			Study area
				<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>L_∞</i>	<i>k</i>	<i>t₀</i>	
Cihangir et al. (1997)	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	586	∑	0.0010	3.20				Northern Aegean Sea
Avşar (2001)	<i>Squalus acanthias</i>	328	∑	0.0040	2.95	157	0.12	-1.30	SE Black Sea
Erdem et al. (2001)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	54	∑	0.0026	3.20				Southern Black Sea
Filiz and Mater (2002)	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	14	∑	0.0085	2.93				Northern Aegean Sea
	<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	24		0.0008	3.32				
	<i>Raja clavata</i>	29		0.0016	3.29				
	<i>Raja miraletus</i>	13		0.0001	4.02				
	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	110		0.0016	3.18				
	<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	20		0.0488	2.69				
İşmen (2003)	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	256	∑	0.0014	3.31	121.5	0.09	-1.61	Iskenderun Bay
Filiz and Bilge (2004)	<i>Chimaera monstrosa</i>	17	∑	0.0028	2.82				Sığacık Bay
	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	29		0.0149	2.81				
	<i>Dipturus oxyrinchus</i>	8		0.0007	3.40				
	<i>Gymnura altavela</i>	9		0.0268	2.96				
	<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	35		0.0011	3.25				
	<i>Myliobatis aquila</i>	14		0.0008	3.34				
	<i>Raja clavata</i>	37		0.0016	3.30				
	<i>Raja miraletus</i>	13		0.0001	4.15				
	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	637		0.0012	3.26				
	<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	37		0.0273	2.91				
Başçınar and Sağlam (2005)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	193	∑	0.0023	3.24				SE Black Sea
Demirhan et al. (2005)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	52	∑	0.0010	3.42				SE Black Sea
Düzgüneş et al. (2006)	<i>Squalus acanthias</i>	182	♀	0.0014	3.25				SE Black Sea
		85		♂	0.0010	3.31			
Karakulak et al. (2006)	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	12	∑	0.1168	2.12				Gökçeada Island
	<i>Raja radula</i>	25		0.0030	3.21				
	<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	22		0.0139	3.10				
Türker-Çakır et al. (2006)	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	291	∑	6E-7	2.92				Edremit Bay
Demirhan and Can (2007)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	27	∑	0.0019	3.24				SE Black Sea
Demirhan and Seyhan (2007)	<i>Squalus acanthias</i>	151	♀	4E-7	3.51	137.73	0.12	1.67	SE Black Sea
		24		♂	8E-7	3.31	123.78	0.16	

	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	48		0.0126	3.30*				
	<i>Dipturus oxyrinchus</i>	118		0.0042	3.29				
	<i>Etmopterus spinax</i>	24		0.0017	3.27				
	<i>Galeus melastomus</i>	93		0.0024	3.03				
	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	1501		0.0017	3.17				
	<i>Heptranchias perlo</i>	14		0.0042	2.93				
	<i>Hexanchus griseus</i>	5		8E-5	3.82				
İşmen et al. (2007a)	<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	26	Σ	0.0013	3.19				Saros Bay
	<i>Myliobatis aquila</i>	14		0.0125	3.02				
	<i>Raja clavata</i>	112		0.0132	3.12*				
	<i>Raja miraletus</i>	30		0.0089	3.22*				
	<i>Raja radula</i>	49		0.0113	3.25*				
	<i>Rostroraja alba</i>	43		0.0066	3.20*				
	<i>Squalus blainville</i>	299		0.0034	3.06				
	<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	20		0.0592	2.64				
İşmen et al. (2007b)	<i>Rhinobatos rhinobatos</i>	225	Σ	0.0036	2.93	128.6	0.29	-0.89	Iskenderun Bay
	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	16		0.0149	3.25				
	<i>Gymnura altavela</i>	17		0.0449	2.84				
	<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	17		0.0044	2.91				
Özaydın et al. (2007)	<i>Raja miraletus</i>	12	Σ	0.0063	2.95				Izmir Bay
	<i>Rostroraja alba</i>	11		0.0090	3.47				
	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	187		0.0006	3.44				
	<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	12		0.0535	2.39				
	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	334		0.0020	3.24				
	<i>Gymnura altavela</i>	107		0.0090	3.23				
Yeldan and Avşar (2007)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	77	Σ	0.0037	3.08				NE Mediterranean
	<i>Raja radula</i>	295		0.0012	3.36				
	<i>Raja asterias</i>	113		0.0008	3.35				
Başusta et al. (2008)	<i>Rhinobatos rhinobatos</i>	66	♀	0.0014	3.16	154.88	0.13	-1.26	Iskenderun Bay
		49	♂	0.0012	3.19	121.65	0.31	-0.13	
Hepkafadar (2008)	<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	190	Σ	0.1060	2.27				Izmir Bay
	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	31		0.0102	3.37*				
	<i>Gymnura altavela</i>	9		0.0025	3.27*				
	<i>Myliobatis aquila</i>	39		0.0058	3.28*				
	<i>Raja clavata</i>	24		0.0335	2.89*				
	<i>Raja miraletus</i>	10		0.0346	2.82*				
İlkyaz et al. (2008)	<i>Raja polystigma</i>	18	Σ	0.0218	3.05*				Izmir Bay
	<i>Rostroraja alba</i>	5		0.0083	3.13*				
	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	744		0.0012	3.29				
	<i>Scyliorhinus stellaris</i>	11		0.0020	3.23				
	<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	148		0.0027	3.05				
	<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	35		0.0232	2.98				
Yeldan et al. (2008)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	90	Σ	0.0034	3.10	79.66	0.13	-3.03	NE Mediterranean
Türker-Çakır et al. (2008)	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	112	Σ	2E-6	3.10				Edremit Bay

İşmen et al. (2009)	<i>Etmopterus spinax</i>	11		0.0023	3.23					
	<i>Galeus melastomus</i>	303		0.0016	3.18					
	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	1888		0.0017	3.17					
	<i>Scyliorhinus stellaris</i>	12		0.0009	3.36					
	<i>Hexanchus griseus</i>	7	Σ	0.0002	3.61					Saros Bay
	<i>Heptanchias perlo</i>	18		0.0047	2.90					
	<i>Mustelus asterias</i>	7		0.0006	3.40					
	<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	70		0.0034	2.98					
	<i>Squalus acanthias</i>	565		0.0037	3.04					
	<i>Squalus blainville</i>	27		0.0030	3.07					
Özütemiz et al. (2009)	<i>Galeus melastomus</i>	130		0.0020	3.04					
	<i>Squalus blainville</i>	135	Σ	0.0010	3.30					Sığacık Bay
Yarmaz (2009)	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	10		0.5092	1.76					
	<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	60		4.9504	1.77					
	<i>Myliobatis aquila</i>	12		0.0140	3.18					
	<i>Raja clavata</i>	33	Σ	0.0322	2.60					
	<i>Raja miraletus</i>	13		0.0215	2.57					
	<i>Raja radula</i>	23		0.0029	3.21					
	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	108		8E-6	2.88					
	<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	9		0.1297	2.47					
Yeldan et al. (2009)	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	346	Σ	0.0033	3.14	294.94	0.03	-2.20		NE Mediterranean
Yığın and İşmen (2009)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	226		0.0016	3.32					
	<i>Raja miraletus</i>	52		0.0017	3.27					
	<i>Raja radula</i>	204		0.0020	3.32					
	<i>Rostroraja alba</i>	126	Σ	0.0019	3.27					
	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	71		0.0007	3.55					
	<i>Dipturus oxyrinchus</i>	179		0.0008	3.35					
	<i>Myliobatis aquila</i>	66		0.0002	3.56					
Bilge et al. (2010)	<i>Etmopterus spinax</i>	116	Σ	0.0031	3.12					Sığacık Bay
Yığın and İşmen (2010a)	<i>Dipturus oxyrinchus</i>	89	♀	0.0008	3.37	233.88	0.04	-1.34		
		90	♂	0.0009	3.34	251.81	0.04	-0.92		Saros Bay
Yığın and İşmen (2010b)	<i>Rostroraja alba</i>	126	Σ	0.0019	3.27	311	0.04	-0.25		Saros Bay
Bök et al. (2011)	<i>Raja asterias</i>	30		2E-6	3.24					
	<i>Raja clavata</i>	24	Σ	1E-5	2.87					
	<i>Squalus blainville</i>	18		4E-5	2.48					
	<i>Squalus acanthias</i>	8		3E-5	2.61					
Saygu (2011)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	792		0.0018	3.25					
	<i>Raja miraletus</i>	153		0.0011	3.43					
	<i>Raja radula</i>	62	Σ	0.0018	3.30					
	<i>Dipturus oxyrinchus</i>	105		0.0012	3.28					
	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	18		0.0018	3.37					
Başusta et al. (2012)	<i>Aetomylaeus bovinus</i>	22		0.0194	2.90					
	<i>Raja clavata</i>	75		0.0230	2.64*					
	<i>Raja miraletus</i>	22		0.0021	3.26*					
	<i>Rhinobatos rhinobatos</i>	20		0.0011	3.19					
	<i>Glaucostegus cemiculus</i>	262	Σ	0.0026	3.02					
	<i>Gymnura altavela</i>	104		0.0170	2.79*					
	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	417		0.0419	3.31*					
	<i>Rhinoptera marginata</i>	17		0.0100	2.14					
<i>Tetronarce nobiliana</i>	92		0.0150	3.06						

Demirel and Dalkara (2012)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	170	Σ	0.1130	2.42*					Sea of Marmara
	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	189		0.0040	2.86					
Güven et al. (2012)	<i>Centrophorus granulosus</i>	56	Σ	0.0010	3.41					Antalya Bay
	<i>Etmopterus spinax</i>	150		0.0052	2.94					
	<i>Galeus melastomus</i>	544		0.0026	3.00					
	<i>Heptanchias perlo</i>	11		0.0021	3.08					
	<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	4		0.0974	2.77					
	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	647		0.0012	3.27					
Yığın and İşmen (2012)	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	52	♀	0.0008	3.51	186.54	0.05	-1.40		Northern Aegean Sea
		32		♂	0.0005					
Duman and Başusta (2013)	<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	117	Σ	0.0195	2.99	57.32	0.18	-0.39		Iskenderun Bay
Kasapoğlu and Düzgüneş (2013)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	63	Σ	0.0100	3.29					Southern and SE Black Sea
Özdemir and Duyar (2013)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	102	Σ	0.0027	3.18					Southern Black Sea
Bilge et al. (2014)	<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	74	Σ	0.0053	2.84					Sığacık Bay
	<i>Mustelus punctulatus</i>	52		0.0224	3.03					
	<i>Raja miraletus</i>	62		0.0008	3.44					
	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	144		0.0012	3.30					
	<i>Scyliorhinus stellaris</i>	92		0.0039	2.96					
	<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	57		0.0519	2.72					
Deval et al. (2014)	<i>Bathytoshia lata</i>	4	Σ	0.0030	3.00					Antalya Bay
	<i>Leucoraja circularis</i>	6		0.0039	3.08					
Eronat and Özaydın (2014)	<i>Chimaera monstrosa</i>	97	Σ	0.0076	3.27					Izmir and Sığacık Bays
	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	78		0.0011	3.45					
	<i>Dipturus oxyrinchus</i>	8		0.0017	3.13					
	<i>Etmopterus spinax</i>	129		0.0035	3.08					
	<i>Galeus melastomus</i>	235		0.0019	3.14					
	<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	41		0.0010	3.27					
	<i>Mustelus punctulatus</i>	6		0.0224	3.04					
	<i>Myliobatis aquila</i>	54		0.0005	3.41					
	<i>Raja asterias</i>	17		0.0007	3.47					
	<i>Raja clavata</i>	137		0.0007	3.50					
	<i>Raja radula</i>	16		0.0017	3.33					
	<i>Rostroraja alba</i>	10		0.0016	3.32					
	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	1210		0.0012	3.26					
<i>Scyliorhinus stellaris</i>	19	0.0006	3.46							
<i>Squalus blainville</i>	308	0.0048	2.96							
<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	107	0.0230	2.95							
Yığın and İşmen (2014)	<i>Raja radula</i>	142	♀	0.0019	3.36	82.94	0.16	-0.59		Saros Bay
		113		♂	0.0022					
Akalm et al. (2015)	<i>Gymnura altavela</i>	7	Σ	0.0156	3.09					Çandarlı Bay
	<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	10		0.0208	3.09					
Eronat and Özaydın (2015)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	106	♀	0.6420	2.84					Sığacık Bay
		81		♂	0.6560					
Özbek et al. (2015)	<i>Bathytoshia lata</i>	5	Σ	1E-4	4.04					Antalya Bay
	<i>Dasyatis marmorata</i>	21		0.0020	3.23					
	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	391		0.0230	2.76					
Yapıcı et al. (2015)	<i>Rostroraja alba</i>	12	Σ	0.0021	3.21					Sığacık Bay
Başusta (2016)	<i>Carcharhinus plumbeus</i>	55	Σ	0.0100	2.87					Iskenderun Bay
Girgin and Başusta (2016)	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	209	♀	0.0272	3.06*					Iskenderun Bay
		175		♂	0.0247					

Kaya and Başusta (2016)	<i>Tetronarce nobiliana</i>	93	Σ	0.0151	3.06	74.47	0.11	-1.06	Iskenderun Bay
Özbek et al. (2016)	<i>Gymnura altavela</i>	172	Σ	0.0031	2.93				Antalya Bay
Öztekin et al. (2016)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	62		0.0081	2.96				Gallipoli Peninsula
	<i>Raja radula</i>	10		0.0035	3.24				
	<i>Rostroraja alba</i>	11	Σ	0.0012	3.37				
	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	22		0.0238	2.52				
	<i>Squalus blainville</i>	14		0.0053	2.95				
Yığın and İşmen (2016)	<i>Squalus acanthias</i>	346	♀			101.21	0.15	-0.68	Saros Bay
		274	♂			72.85	0.27	-0.24	
Çalık and Erdoğan-Sağlam (2017)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	10	Σ	0.0010	3.44				SE Black Sea
Gönülal (2017)	<i>Dalatias licha</i>	4	Σ	0.0184	3.20				Northern Aegean Sea
	<i>Etmopterus spinax</i>	12	Σ	0.3514	1.76				
	<i>Galeus melastomus</i>	26	♀	0.0003	3.65				
		13	♂	0.1746	2.08				
	<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	11	Σ	0.0014	3.31				
	<i>Prionace glauca</i>	6	Σ	0.0105	3.85				
	<i>Scyliorhinus stellaris</i>	28	Σ	0.0410	3.10				
Özdemir (2017)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	259	Σ	0.0013	3.35				Southern Black Sea
Yemişken (2017)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	66		0.0100	3.16				Iskenderun Bay
		19		0.0127	3.13				Gökçeada Island
	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	132		0.0012	3.30				Iskenderun Bay
		202		0.0029	3.03				Gökçeada Island
	<i>Gymnura altavela</i>	12		0.0059	3.03				
	<i>Glaucostegus cemiculus</i>	16		0.0100	2.73				
	<i>Raja asterias</i>	55	Σ	0.0009	3.44				Iskenderun Bay
		13		0.4474	2.29				
		30		0.0015	3.18				
		12		0.0010	3.38				Gökçeada Island
<i>Scyliorhinus stellaris</i>	14		0.0018	3.20					
Başusta and Aslan (2018)	<i>Aetomylaeus bovinus</i>	47	♀	0.0625	2.90*	242.59*	0.05	-1.90	NE Mediterranean
		47	♂	0.0351	3.09*	238.43*	0.04	-2.98	
Bengil et al. (2018)	<i>Glaucostegus cemiculus</i>	117	Σ	0.0021	3.12				Izmir Bay
		266		0.0015	3.66				Iskenderun Bay
Bilgin and Köse (2018)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	117	Σ	0.0039	3.13				SE Black Sea
İşmen et al. (2018)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	130		0.0006	3.53				Sea of Marmara
	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	45	Σ	0.0007	3.39				
	<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	17		0.0195	2.98				
Kara et al. (2018)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	33	Σ	0.0020	3.25				Izmir Bay
	<i>Squatina squatina</i>	3		0.0203	2.75				
Özcan and Başusta (2018a)	<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	155	Σ	0.0027	3.00	195.13	0.06	-4.27	Iskenderun Bay
Özcan and Başusta (2018b)	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	1150	Σ	0.0013	3.23	56.70	0.20	-1.60	Iskenderun Bay
Torcu-Koç and Erdoğan (2018)	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	48	♀	0.0080	2.91				Bandırma Bay
		43	♂	0.0040	3.09				
Yeldan (2018)	<i>Gymnura altavela</i>	150	♀	0.1310	3.21	136.25*	0.38	-0.58	Iskenderun Bay
		134	♂	0.0990	3.14	131.25	0.25	-0.49	
Yeldan and Gündoğdu (2018)	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	72	Σ	0.0390	2.93*	58.28*	0.06	-0.21	Iskenderun Bay
	<i>Dasyatis marmorata</i>	143		0.0480	2.94*	46.09*	0.36	-0.16	

	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	10		0.1306	2.17				
	<i>Mustelus mustelus</i>	60		0.1139	2.71				
	<i>Myliobatis aquila</i>	12		0.0014	3.18				
	<i>Raja clavata</i>	33		0.0322	2.56				
Türker et al. (2019)	<i>Raja miraletus</i>	13	∑	0.0215	2.56				Edremit Bay
	<i>Raja radula</i>	23		0.0029	3.21				
	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	108		6E-5	2.88				
	<i>Scyliorhinus stellaris</i>	8		0.0004	3.64				
	<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	9		0.1297	2.47				
Başusta et al. (2020)	<i>Glaucostegus cemiculus</i>	166	♀	0.0018	3.10	187.17	0.19	-1.38	Iskenderun Bay
		125	♂	0.0017	3.12	144.85	0.32	-1.13	
Özdemir et al. (2020)	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	12	∑	0.0028	3.22				Southern Black Sea
	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	1143		0.0012	3.26				
	<i>Scyliorhinus stellaris</i>	110		0.0009	3.37				
	<i>Galeus melastomus</i>	795		0.0017	3.14				
	<i>Etmopterus spinax</i>	575		0.0036	3.02				
Cabbar and Yiğın (2021a)	<i>Squalus acanthias</i>	48	∑	0.0023	3.16				Gökçeada Island
	<i>Raja clavata</i>	255		0.0009	3.45				
	<i>Raja miraletus</i>	29		0.0001	3.91				
	<i>Dipturus oxyrinchus</i>	36		0.0006	3.43				
Cabbar and Yiğın (2021b)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	76	♀	0.0030	3.18	106.54	0.16	-0.28	Northern Aegean Sea
		28	♂	0.0223	2.68	101.71	0.18	-0.07	
Onay and Dalgıç (2021)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	478	∑	0.0027	3.20				SE Black Sea
Özdemir et al. (2021)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	430	∑	0.0032	3.25				Southern Black Sea
	<i>Dalatias licha</i>	42		0.0180	2.87				
	<i>Etmopterus spinax</i>	1057		0.0060	2.90				
	<i>Galeus melastomus</i>	1722		0.0025	3.00				
	<i>Raja clavata</i>	294		0.0012	3.36				
Soykan and Kınacıgil (2021)	<i>Dipturus oxyrinchus</i>	63	∑	0.0007	3.37				Sığacık and Kuşadası Bays
	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	2940		0.0015	3.19				
	<i>Squalus acanthias</i>	133		0.0020	3.22				
	<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	70		0.0410	2.70				
Yiğın and İşmen (2021)	<i>Raja miraletus</i>	52	∑	0.0017	3.27	62.43	0.28	-0.54	Saros Bay
Acarlı et al. (2022)	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	147	∑	0.0012	3.28				Gökçeada Island
Başusta et al. (2022)	<i>Rhinoptera marginata</i>	224	∑			178.60*	0.12	-2.08	Iskenderun Bay
Başusta and Özel (2022)	<i>Dipturus oxyrinchus</i>	143	♀	0.0023	3.10	152.55	0.06	-1.62	Iskenderun Bay
		112	♂	0.0009	3.34	161.73	0.06	-1.63	
Bengil (2022)	<i>Squalus blainville</i>	184	∑	0.0010	3.33				Eastern Mediterranean
Daban et al. (2022)	<i>Raja clavata</i>	147	♀	0.0007	3.53				Gökçeada Island
		115	♂	0.0012	3.38				
Dağtekin et al. (2022)	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	224		0.0004	3.73				Southern Black Sea
	<i>Raja clavata</i>	1408	∑	0.0042	3.09				
	<i>Squalus acanthias</i>	108		0.0068	2.87				
Gül et al. (2022)	<i>Oxynotus centrina</i>	21	∑	0.02	2.82				Sea of Marmara
Kabasakal and Özbek (2022)	<i>Oxynotus centrina</i>	18	♀	0.216	2.68				Mediterranean
		10	♂	0.134	3.04				

	<i>Raja miraletus</i>	9		0.0024	3.17				
	<i>Raja clavata</i>	40		0.0088	2.84				
Karadurmuş (2022)	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	92	∑	0.0265	2.62				Sea of Marmara
	<i>Squalus acanthias</i>	22		0.0073	2.89				
	<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	46		0.0564	2.69				
	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	349		0.0022	3.18				
Taylan et al. (2022)	<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	5	∑	0.0108	3.20				Izmir Bay
	<i>Gymnura altavela</i>	7		0.9109	3.22				
	<i>Squalus acanthias</i>	316	♀	0.0098	2.85				
Özdemir et al. (2023)		260	♂	0.0103	2.28				Southern Black Sea
	<i>Raja clavata</i>	262	♀			102.46	0.16	0.72	
Yığın et al. (2023)			♂			93.04	0.17	0.48	Gökçeada Island
	<i>Squalus blainville</i>	39	♀	0.00005	3.81				
Kabasakal et al. (2024)		28	♂	0.00002	3.11				Sea of Marmara
	<i>Myliobatis aquila</i>	41	♀	0.0012	3.20	164.08	0.95	-0.08	
Özten et al. (2024)		44	♂	(∑)	(∑)	138.59	0.90	-0.09	Saros Bay
	<i>Galeus melastomus</i>	106	♀	0.002	3.13				
Cengiz et al. (2024)		230	♂	0.003	2.94				Mediterranean
	<i>Raja clavata</i>	50		0.0013	3.33				
Şen and Özekinci (2024)	<i>Torpedo marmorata</i>	34	∑	0.0422	2.77				Kemer Bay
	<i>Dasyatis pastinaca</i>	8		0.0156	2.75				
	<i>Squalus blainville</i>	48	∑	0.0005	3.03				Iskenderun Bay

N, number of sample studied; ♀, female; ♂, male; ∑, both sexes; *a*, intercept; *b*, slope; L_{∞} , asymptotic length; *k*, growth coefficient (year⁻¹); t_0 , theoretical age at length equal to zero; *, using disc width.

Table 2 highlights that bio-ecological studies have been conducted on batoids 162 times, on sharks 102 times, and on chimeras only twice. In this context, the bio-ecologically most studied batoid species is *Raja clavata* (38 times), followed by *Dasyatis pastinaca* (24 times), *Torpedo marmorata* (17 times), *Raja miraletus* (14 times), *Gymnura altavela* and *Raja radula* (10 times each). Of the remaining species, *Dipturus oxyrinchus* was studied 6 times, *Myliobatis aquila* and *Rostroraja alba* were 8 times each, *Glaucostegus cemiculus* and *Raja asterias* were 4 times each, *Rhinobatos rhinobatos* and *Tetronarce nobiliana* were 3 times each, *Aetomylaeus bovinus*, *Bathytoshia lata*, *Dasyatis marmorata* and *Rhinoptera marginata* were 2 times each, *Leucoraja circularis* and *Raja polystigma* were once each. On the other hand, the shark species most frequently studied is *Scyliorhinus canicula*, researched 24 times, followed by *Mustelus mustelus* at 14 times, *Squalus acanthias* and *Squalus blainville* at 11 times each. The remaining species studied included *Galeus melastomus* (10 times), *Etmopterus spinax* and *Scyliorhinus stellaris* (8 times each), *Heptranchias perlo* (3 times), *Dalatias licha*, *Hexanchus griseus*, *Mustelus punctulatus*, and *Oxynotus centrina* (twice each), and *Carcharhinus plumbeus*, *Centrophorus granulosus*, *Mustelus asterias*, *Prionace glauca*, and *Squatina squatina* (once each). *Chimaera monstrosa*, the sole species of Chimaera in Turkish marine waters, has only been examined in two bio-ecological studies thus far.

Figure 4. Box-Whiskers plots showing the exponent b of LWR studies conducted for 37 cartilaginous species on the Turkish coast. The central box covers 50% of the b values, the vertical line indicates the range of the values, and the horizontal line represents the median.

In general, the values of the exponent b are expected to vary between 2 and 4 (Tesch, 1971). Extreme exponent b values were obtained as 1.76 for *Dasyatis pastinaca* (Yarmaz, 2009) and *Etmopterus spinax* (Gönülal, 2017), and 4.15 for *Raja miraletus* (Filiz and Bilge, 2004) from the LWR studies in Turkish marine waters, probably due to the very low number of samples. The median of b is 3.17, with 25-75% of these values ranging between 2.93 and 3.30 (Figure 4). The mean value of all b is 3.10 (± 0.34), which is significantly different from 3.00 ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 5. Percentage of studies on bio-ecological characteristics of cartilaginous species for each Turkish sea.

Figure 5 indicates that the part of the Turkish coast where cartilaginous species are most studied is the Aegean Sea, accounting for 44% with 42 instances, followed by the Mediterranean at 30% with 28 instances, the Black Sea at 19% with 18 instances, and the Sea of Marmara at 7% with 7 instances. Regarding the distribution of bio-ecological studies on the group of cartilaginous fish, in the Aegean Sea, 55% of 42 studies focused on batoids, 44% on sharks, and 1% on chimaeras; in the Mediterranean, 77% of 28 studies were on batoids and 23% on sharks; in the Black Sea, 74% of 18 studies focused on batoids and 26% on sharks; and in the Marmara Sea, 55% of 7 studies were on batoids and 45% on sharks (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Map reflecting the percentage distribution of bioecological studies according to cartilaginous fish groups in each sea of Türkiye.

Genetic studies

Genetic studies published so far on cartilaginous fishes in Turkish marine waters are quite limited. There is no study other than Turan (2008), Bengil (2018), Bengil et al. (2019), Tüney-Kızılkaya and Bengil (2022) and Turan et al. (2024d).

Turan (2008) revealed the phylogenetic relationship and systematic patterns among nine skate species (*Rostroraja alba*, *Leucoraja fullonica*, *Dipturus oxyrinchus*, *D. batis*, *Raja clavata*, *R. montagui*, *R. asterias*, *R. miraletus*, and *R. radula*) in the Mediterranean and the Black Sea with the mtDNA *16S rRNA* dataset. 39 variable and 29 parsimony informative sites were provided from the *16S rRNA* sequences, and the average nucleotide diversity was found to be 0.018. Homogeneity was observed in the genetic distance values between *R. clavata* and *R. montagui*. The highest genetic difference value (0.040) was observed between *D. oxyrinchus* and *R. asterias*, while the lowest was observed between *R. montagui* and *R. miraletus*, and *R. clavata* and *R. miraletus*. The Neighbour-Joining phylogenetic tree revealed four evolutionary lineages; the first lineage included *R. clavata*, *R. montagui*, and *R. miraletus*, and in the second lineage, *L. fullonica* and *R. asterias* were grouped

together. In the third lineage, *D. batis* and *D. oxyrinchus* were grouped together, resulting in a close relationship with *R. radula*. Moreover, *R. alba* was separated from other species as the most differently grouped species.

Bengil (2018) investigated the genetic characterization of nine elasmobranch species (*Carcharhinus plumbeus*, *Mustelus mustelus*, *M. punctulatus*, *Isurus oxyrinchus*, *Torpedo marmorata*, *Dasyatis pastinaca*, *Gymnura altavela* and *Squatina squatina*) from mtDNA *COI* dataset. In this PhD study, the obtained sequences were compared with other *COI* sequences in both GenBank and the BOLD system, a Neighbour-Joining tree was produced, and the results were also mapped by performing Network analysis.

Bengil et al. (2019) carried out the phylogenetic analysis of *Isurus oxyrinchus* on Eastern Mediterranean coasts of Türkiye using the mtDNA *COI* dataset. They created a phylogenetic mitochondrial haplotype network for the three individuals they used and showed that species with metapopulations were supported.

Tüney-Kızılkaya and Bengil (2022) performed genetic characterization of critically endangered angelsharks *Squatina squatina* and *S. aculeata* obtained from the Aegean Sea based on the mtDNA *COI* and *16S rRNA* sequences. The Neighbour Joining and Maximum Likelihood phylogenetic trees derived from both genes provide similar results, with both trees consisting of four main clades representing the same regional groups: Europe, North Africa, and Asia; South Africa; Australia; and North and South America. In both trees, *S. squatina* sample from the study formed a branch with other *S. squatina* sequences from GenBank. Similarly, *S. aculeata* specimen appeared on a branch among other *S. aculeata* sequences in GenBank. They emphasized that adopting morphological identification as the sole tool is not sufficient to accurately identify *Squatina* spp. and that both morphological and molecular tools should be used to taxonomically identify endangered shark species to secure their conservation status.

Turan et al. (2024d) determined the phylogenetic relationships of seven shark species (*Squalus blainville*, *Carcharhinus plumbeus*, *Galeus melastomus*, *Scyliorhinus canicula*, *Isurus oxyrinchus*, *Mustelus mustelus*, and *Oxynotus centrina*) collected from Iskenderun Bay, using mtDNA *Cyt b* region. 293 variable and 74 conservative nucleotide sites were obtained from *Cyt b* sequences, and 279 of them were informative. Overall nucleotide diversity was found to be 0.43. This study, in which the nucleotide diversity of *Cyt b* sequences was generally observed to be low, revealed that *Oxynotus centrina* had the lowest nucleotide diversity (0.024) and *Galeus melastomus* had the highest nucleotide diversity (0.087). The lowest genetic distance was between *M. mustelus* and *S. canicula*, and the highest between *G. melastomus* and *I. oxyrinchus*. The Neighbour-Joining tree identified two major phylogenetic nodes; at the first main node, *I. oxyrinchus* branched out as a single species, and at the second main node, four sub-branches were identified, with each sub-branch containing a species with a high bootstrap value. The maximum Parsimony tree also identified two major phylogenetic nodes but showed a different topology compared to the Neighbour-Joining tree. At the first node, *G. melastomus* was branched separately, at the second node, close groupings were observed in four sub-branches between *O. centrina* - *S. blainville* and between *C. plumbeus* - *I. oxyrinchus*. The study underlines the need for urgent conservation strategies adapted for these shark species due to low genetic diversity and the presence of regional haplotypes.

Conclusions

This paper focuses on the list of elasmobranch species and explores the status and conservation strategies of elasmobranch species based on available bio-ecological and genetic references in Turkish marine waters. A large part of the elasmobranchs distributed throughout Türkiye and even the Mediterranean are at risk of extinction. However, there are still knowledge gaps that need to be addressed for better understanding and protection. Stocks of cartilaginous fish in Türkiye have been decreasing for many years due to excessive and IUU fisheries (illegal, unregistered, and unregulated fishing) (Öztürk, 2009). Unfortunately, in Turkish fisheries statistics, elasmobranch data are used under general nomenclatures such as “sharks”, “angel sharks” and “rays”. The first step in developing conservation strategies for threatened cartilaginous species should be to include these fish, species by species, in official fisheries statistics.

On the other hand, studies on the distribution of elasmobranch species, determining their share in fishery activities and their bioecology are not sufficient to ensure sustainable stocks. Evaluating genetic diversity levels with bio-ecological parameters together is critically importance to manage effectively marine stocks (Uyan et al. 2024; Uyan and Turan, 2024). In addition, it is important to know the genetic variations are diverse in different mtDNA regions containing informative sites and nuclear markers to make regulations that support the sustainability and protection of elasmobranch stocks. Thus, there is an urgent need for species-specific conservation strategies and dynamic regulations based on the reproductive periods of elasmobranchs (Yığın et al., 2015).

Besides shark and batoid species, the catching of which is prohibited by Communiqué No. 5/1, according to the IUCN criteria, shark (*Carcharias taurus*) and batoid (*Dipturus batis*, *Aetomylaeus bovinus*, *Myliobatis aquila*, and *Rhinoptera marginata*) species listed as Critically Endangered (CR), along with shark (*Echinorhinus brucus*, *Centrophorus uyato*, *Rhincodon typus*, *Odontaspis ferox*, *Mustelus mustelus*, and *Carcharhinus obscurus*) and batoid (*Leucoraja circularis*, *Raja radula*, *Raja undulata*, *Rostroraja alba*, *Himantura leoparda*, *Himantura uarnak*, and *Gymnura altavela*) species listed as Endangered (EN), should also receive legal protection in Turkish marine waters. Moreover, plans for the establishment of marine protected areas should be prioritized, considering the existence of important factors such as the destruction of elasmobranch habitats and harmful pollutants. Otherwise, many endangered cartilaginous species will inevitably become extinct in Turkish marine waters and these species will only be seen in books or museums in the future. Consequently, establishing collaborations between stakeholders, scientists, and policymakers to develop all these strategies is noteworthy in terms of the sustainability of cartilaginous fish stocks.

Acknowledgements

This study was carried out within the scope of the project (1059B192301583) supported by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye (TÜBİTAK).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Author Contributions

C.T., A.U., A.S., S.A.D., and D.E. drafted the main manuscript text. Authors reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Ethical Approval Statements

Local Ethics Committee Approval was not obtained because experimental animals were not used in this study.

Data Availability Statement

The data used in the present study are available upon request from the corresponding author.

References

- Acarlı, D., Kale, S., Çakır, K. (2022). Length–Weight Relationships of Eighteen Fishes and a Cephalopod from Gökçeada Island, Northern Aegean Sea, Turkey. *Thalassas: An International Journal of Marine Sciences*, 38(1), 479-486.
- Agustin, T. I., Risma, R., Sari, R., Setyawan, D. (2023). The Microstructure and Potential of Chondroitin Sulfate in Shark Cartilage Extract. *Squalen Bulletin of Marine and Fisheries Postharvest and Biotechnology*, 18(2), 74-80.
- Akalın, S., İlhan, D., Özeydin, O. (2015). Length-Weight Relationships for 30 Demersal Fish Species from Çandarlı Bay (North Aegean Sea, Turkey). *Croatian Journal of Fisheries: Ribarstvo*, 73(2), 73-76.
- Amri, U., Diharmi, A., Sukmiwati, M. (2021). Characteristics of Catfish Oil, Red Palm Oil and Shark Liver Oil as Functional Foods. *Depik*, 10(2), 151-160.
- Avşar, D. (2001). Age, Growth, Reproduction and Feeding of the Spurdog (*Squalus acanthias* Linnaeus, 1758) in the South-Eastern Black Sea. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 52(2), 269-278.
- Aydoğdu, E. Ö. A., Kesiktaş, M., Şanlı, N. Ö., Güngör, N. D., Sancar, S., Yıldız, T., Yemişken, E. (2023). Preliminary Study on Antimicrobial Activities of Skin Mucus from By-Catch of Species. *Oceanological and Hydrobiological Studies*, 52(2), 137-146.
- Bak, J. G., Kim, J., Ohk, S. H. (2022). Preparation of Shark Byproduct Extract and Gellan Gum based Antibacterial Film Containing Green Tea Extract. *Biomedical Science Letters*, 28(1), 50-57.
- Başçınar N. S. Sağlam H. (2005). Feeding Habits of Thornback Ray (*Raja clavata*), Scorpion Fish (*Scorpaena porcus*) and stargazer (*Uranoscopus scaber*) in the Eastern Black Sea. *Turkish Journal of Aquatic Life*, Special Issue 3(4), 165-169.
- Başusta, N., Demirhan, S. A., Çiçek, E., Başusta, A., Kuleli, T. (2008). Age and Growth of the Common Guitarfish, *Rhinobatos rhinobatos*, in Iskenderun Bay (North-eastern Mediterranean, Turkey). *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 88(4), 837-842.
- Başusta, A., Başusta, N., Sulikowski, J. A., Driggers III, W. B., Demirhan, S. A., Çiçek, E. (2012). Length–Weight Relationships for Nine Species of Batoids from the Iskenderun Bay, Turkey. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 28(5), 850-851.

- Başusta, N. (2016). Length-Weight Relationship of Sandbar Shark *Carcharhinus plumbeus* (Nardo, 1827) in Iskenderun Bay (North-eastern Mediterranean Sea. In: Rapports et Procès-Verbaux des Réunions de la Commission Internationale pour l'Exploration Scientifique de la Mer Méditerranée, 12-16 September 2016, Kiel, Germany. p. 318.
- Başusta, N., Başusta, A., Özbek, E. Ö. (2016). Cartilaginous Fishes and Fisheries in the Mediterranean Coast of Turkey. In The Turkish Part of the Mediterranean Sea; Marine Biodiversity, Fisheries, Conservation and Governance (pp. 248-274). Turkish Marine Research Foundation (TUDAV).
- Başusta, N., Aslan, E. (2018). Age and Growth of Bull Ray *Aetomylaeus bovinus* (Chondrichthyes: Myliobatidae) from the Northeastern Mediterranean Coast of Turkey. *Cahiers de Biologie Marine*, 59, 107-114.
- Başusta, N., Başusta, A., Tıraşın, E. M., Sulikowski, J. A. (2020). Age and Growth of the Blackchin Guitarfish *Glaucostegus cemiculus* (Geoffroy Saint-Hilaire, 1817) from Iskenderun Bay (Northeastern Mediterranean). *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 36(6), 880-887.
- Başusta, N., Başusta, A., Çiçek, E., Cicia, A. M., Sulikowski, J. A. (2022). First Estimates of Age and Growth of the Lusitanian Cownose Ray (*Rhinoptera marginata*) from the Mediterranean Sea. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 10(5), 685.
- Başusta, N., Özel, F. V. (2022). Growth Characteristics of Long-nosed Skate *Dipturus oxyrinchus* (Linnaeus, 1758) Inhabiting the Northeastern Mediterranean Sea. *Animals*, 12(23), 3443.
- Bengil, E. G. T. (2018). Genetic Features of Some Cartilaginous Species Inhabiting Aegean and Mediterranean Sea and Bio-Ecological Features of *Glaucostegus cemiculus*. Ege University, Institute of Science. Izmir, p 155.
- Bengil, E. G. T., Başusta, A., Başusta, N. (2018). Length-Weight Relationships of *Glaucostegus cemiculus* (Geoffroy Saint-Hilaire, 1817) from the Aegean Sea and Northeastern Mediterranean Coasts of Turkey. *Journal of the Black Sea/Mediterranean Environment*, 24(1), 1-9.
- Bengil, E. G. T., Akalın, M., Kızılkaya, İ. T., Bengil, F. (2019). Biology of Shortfin Mako Shark (*Isurus oxyrinchus* Rafinesque, 1810) from the Eastern Mediterranean. *Acta Aquatica Turcica*, 15(4), 425-432.
- Bengil, E. G. T. (2022). Biology and ecology of *Squalus blainville* (Risso, 1827) from the eastern Mediterranean. *Thalassas: An International Journal of Marine Sciences*, 38(2), 1423-1432.
- Bilge, G., Filiz, H., Tarkan, A. N. (2010). Length-Weight Relationship of Velvet Belly Lantern Shark *Etmopterus spinax* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Sığacık Bay (Aegean Sea). *Istanbul University Journal of Fisheries & Aquatic Sciences*, 25(1), 1-8.
- Bilge, G., Yapıcı, S., Filiz, H., Cerim, H. (2014). Weight–Length Relations for 103 Fish Species from the Southern Aegean Sea, Turkey. *Acta Ichthyologica et Piscatoria*, 44, 263-269.
- Bilgin, S., Köse, Ö. (2018). Length–Weight Relationships (LWRs) of Target Fish Turbot, *Scophthalmus maximus* (Pleuronectiformes: Scophthalmidae) and Non-Target Fish Thornback Ray, *Raja clavata* (Rajiformes: Rajidae) Caught by Turbot Gill Net Fishery in the Black Sea, Turkey. *Cahiers de Biologie Marine*, 59(6), 615-622.
- Bök, T. D., Göktürk, D., Kahraman, A. E., Alıçlı, T. Z., Acun, T., Ateş, C. (2011). Length-Weight Relationships of 34 Fish Species from the Sea of Marmara, Turkey. *Journal of Animal and Veterinary Advances*, 10(23), 3037-3042.

- Brito, R., Costa, D., Dias, C., Cruz, P., Barros, P. (2023). Chondroitin Sulfate Supplements for Osteoarthritis: A Critical Review. *Cureus*, 15(6), e40192.
- Cabbar, K., Yiğın, C. Ç. (2021a). Length–Weight Relationships of Elasmobranch Species from Gökçeada Island in the Northern Aegean Sea. *Thalassas: An International Journal of Marine Sciences*, 37(2), 497-504.
- Cabbar, K., Yiğın, C. Ç. (2021b). Biology of the Thornback Ray (Linnaeus, 1758) in the North Aegean Sea. *Oceanological and Hydrobiological Studies*, 50(2), 115-127.
- Cailliet, G. M., Musick, J. A., Simpfendorfer, C. A., Stevens, J. D. (2005). Ecology and Life History Characteristics of Chondrichthyan Fish. In *Sharks, Rays and Chimaeras: The Status of the Chondrichthyan Fishes* (pp 12-18). IUCN/SSC Shark Specialist Group.
- Cavanagh, R. D., Gibson, C. (2007). Overview of the Conservation Status of Cartilaginous Fishes (Chondrichthyans) in the Mediterranean Sea (No. 3). IUCN.
- Cengiz, Ç. C., Aydın, C., Ünlüoğlu, A., Akalın, S. (2024). Length-Weight Relationship of the Blackmouth Catshark (*Galeus melastomus* Rafinesque, 1810) on the Turkish Coasts of the Mediterranean Sea. *Tethys Environmental Science*, 1(3), 135-143.
- Cihangir, B., Ünlüoğlu, A., Tıraşın, E. M. (1997). Distribution and Some Biological Aspects of the Lesser Spotted Dogfish (Chondrichthyes, *Scyliorhinus canicula*, Linnaeus, 1758) from the Northern Aegean Sea. In *Proceedings Book. Mediterranean Fisheries Congress, 9-11 April 1997, Izmir, Türkiye*. pp. 585-603.
- Coscueta, E. R., Fernandes, N. C., Brassesco, M. E., Rosa, A., Almeida, A., Pintado, M. M. (2024). Turning Discarded Blue Shark (*Prionace glauca*) Skin into a Valuable Nutraceutical Resource: An Enzymatic Collagen Hydrolysate. *Food Bioscience*, 104472.
- Çalık, S., Erdoğan-Sağlam, N. (2017). Length-Weight Relationships of Demersal Fish Species Caught by Bottom Trawl from Eastern Black Sea (Turkey). *Cahiers de Biologie Marine*, 58(4), 485-490.
- Daban, İ. B., Cabbar, K., Yiğın, C. Ç. (2022). Feeding Ecology of Thornback Ray, *Raja clavata* (Linnaeus 1758) in Gökçeada Island, Northern Aegean Sea, Turkey. *Thalassas: An International Journal of Marine Sciences*, 38(1), 197-211.
- Dağtekin, M., Genç, Y., Kasapoğlu, N., Erik, G., Misir, D. S., İlhan, S., Ok, M., Altuntaş, C., Özsandıkçı, U., Büyükdeveci, F., Kaya, T., Cebeci, A., Saltan, A. N., Haşimoğlu, A., Firidin, Ş. (2022). Length-weight relationships of 28 fish species caught from demersal trawl survey in the Middle Black Sea, Turkey. *Turkish Journal of Zoology*, 46(1), 67-73.
- Danovaro, R., Company, J. B., Corinaldesi, C., D'Onghia, G., Galil, B., Gambi, C., Gooday, A.J., Lampadariou, N., Luna, G.M., Morigi, C., Olu, K., Polymenakou, P., Ramirez-Llodra, E., Sabbatini, A., Sardà, F., Sibuet, M., Tselepides, A. (2010). Deep-sea biodiversity in the Mediterranean Sea: The Known, the Unknown, and the Unknowable. *PloS One*, 5(8), e11832.
- Demirel, N., Dalkara, E. M. (2012). Weight-Length Relationships of 28 Fish Species in the Sea of Marmara. *Turkish Journal of Zoology*, 36(6), 785-791.
- Demirhan, S. A., Engin, S., Seyhan, K., Akamca, E. (2005). Some Biological Aspects of Thornback Ray (*Raja clavata* L., 1758) in the Southeastern Black Sea. *Turkish Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 5(2), 75-83.
- Demirhan, S. A., Can, M. F. (2007). Length–Weight Relationships for Seven Fish Species from the Southeastern Black Sea. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 23(3), 282-283.

- Demirhan, S. A., Seyhan, K. (2007). Life history of spiny dogfish, *Squalus acanthias* (L. 1758), in the southern Black Sea. *Fisheries Research*, 85(1-2), 210-216.
- Deval, M. C., Güven, O., Saygu, İ., Kebapçioğlu, T. (2014). Length-Weight Relationships of 10 Fish Species Found off Antalya Bay, Eastern Mediterranean. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 30(3), 567-568.
- Doğdu, S. A., Turan, C., Gürlek, M., Ayas, D., Ergüden, D. (2022). Genetic, Morphologic and Bio-Ecological Perspective of Randall's Threadfin Bream, *Nemipterus randalli*, in the Eastern Mediterranean Coast, Turkey. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of India*, 64(2), 48-54.
- Dulvy, N. K., Allen, D. J., Ralph, G. M., Walls, R. H. (2016). The Conservation Status of Sharks, Rays, and Chimaeras in the Mediterranean Sea [Brochure]. IUCN.
- Dulvy, N. K., Fowler, S. L., Musick, J. A., Cavanagh, R. D., Kyne, P. M., Harrison, L. R., Carlson, J. K., Davidson, L. N. K., Fordham, S. V., Francis, M. P., Pollock, C. M., Simpfendorfer, C. A., Burgess, G. H., Carpenter, K. E., Compagno, L. J. V., Ebert, D. A., Gibson, C., Heupel, M. R., Livingstone, S. R., Sanciangco, J. C., Stevens, J. D., Valenti, S., White, W. T. (2014). Extinction Risk and Conservation of the World's Sharks and Rays. *eLIFE*, 3, e00590.
- Duman, Ö. V., Başusta, N. (2013). Age and Growth Characteristics of Marbled Electric Ray *Torpedo marmorata* (Risso, 1810) Inhabiting Iskenderun Bay, North-Eastern Mediterranean Sea. *Turkish Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 13(3), 541-549.
- Düzgüneş, E., Okumuş, İ., Feyzioğlu, M., Sivri, N. (2006). Population Parameters of Spiny Dogfish, *Squalus acanthias* from the Turkish Black Sea Coast and Its Commercial Exploitation in Turkey. In *The Proceedings of the Workshop on Mediterranean Cartilaginous Fish with Emphasis on Southern and Eastern Mediterranean* (pp. 1-9). Turkish Marine Research Foundation (TUDAV).
- Ebert, D. A., Fowler, S., Compagno, L. (2013). *Sharks of the World: A Complete Guide*. Princeton University Press.
- Ebert, D. A., Stehmann, M. (2013). *Sharks, Batoids, and Chimaeras of the North Atlantic*. FAO Species Catalogue of Fishery Purpose.
- Erdem, Y., Özdemir, S., Sümer, Ç. (2001). Vatoz (*Raja clavata* L.) Balığının Mide İçeriği Üzerine Bir Araştırma. In: *Proceedings Book. XI. Ulusal Su Ürünleri Sempozyumu*, 4-6 September 2001, Hatay, Türkiye. pp. 351-359. [In Turkish].
- Ergüden, D., Kabasakal, H., and Ayas, D. (2022). Fisheries bycatch and conservation priorities of young sharks in the Eastern Mediterranean. *Zoology in the Middle East*, 68(2), 135-144.
- Eronat, E. G. T., Özaydın, O. (2014). Length-Weight Relationship of Cartilaginous Fish Species from Central Aegean Sea (Izmir Bay and Sığacık Bay). *Ege Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 31(3), 119-125.
- Eronat, E. G. T., Özaydın, O. (2015). Diet Composition of the Thornback Ray, *Raja clavata* Linnaeus, 1758 (Elasmobranchii: Rajidae) in the Turkish Aegean Sea. *Zoology in the Middle East*, 61(1), 38-44.
- FAO. (2024). FishStat: Global capture production 1950-2022. *FishStatJ*. Available at www.fao.org/fishery/en/statistics/software/fishstatj, version (12.07.24).
- Ferretti, F., Osio, G. C., Jenkins, C. J., Rosenberg, A. A., Lotze, H. K. (2013). Long-Term Change in a Meso-Predator Community in Response to Prolonged and Heterogeneous Human Impact. *Scientific Reports*, 3(1), 1057.

- Filiz, H., Mater, S. (2002). A Preliminary Study on Length-Weight Relationships for Seven Elasmobranch Species from North Aegean Sea, Turkey. *Ege Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 19(3-4), 401-409.
- Filiz, H., Bilge, G. (2004). Length-Weight Relationships of 24 Fish Species from the North Aegean Sea, Turkey. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 20 (2004), 431-432.
- Fofandi, D. C., Tanna, P. D., Dabhi, R. M., Motivarash, Y. B. (2020). Properties and Utilization of Shark Skin. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*, 8(1), 623-625.
- Fuochi V., Li Volti G., Camiolo G., Tiralongo F., Giallongo C., Distefano A., Petronio G.P., Barbagallo I., Viola M., Furneri P.M., Di Rosa M., Avola R. Tibullo D. (2017). Antimicrobial and Anti-proliferative Effects of Skin Mucus Derived from *Dasyatis pastinaca* (Linnaeus, 1758). *Marine Drugs*, 15, 342.
- Girgin, H., Baştusta, N. (2016). Testing Staining Techniques to Determine Age and Growth of *Dasyatis pastinaca* (Linnaeus, 1758) Captured in Iskenderun Bay, Northeastern Mediterranean. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 32(3), 595-601.
- Gönülal, O. (2017). Length-Weight Relationships of 16 Fish Species from Deep Water of Northern Aegean Sea (500-900 m). *Turkish Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 17(5), 995-1002.
- Gül, G., Yokeş, M. B., Demirel, N. (2022). The Occurrence and Feeding of a Critically Endangered Shark Species, *Oxynotus centrina* in the Sea of Marmara. *Journal of Fish Biology*, 101(3), 728-735.
- Güven, O., Kebapçioğlu, T., Deval, M. C. (2012). Length-Weight Relationships of Sharks in Antalya Bay, Eastern Mediterranean. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 28(2), 278-279.
- Hepkafadar, O. (2008). Research on Fishery and Some Biological Aspects of Smooth-Hound Shark (*Mustelus mustelus* L., 1758) in Izmir Bay. Ege University, Institute of Science. Izmir, p 70.
- Hole, M., Taylor, K. A. (1996). Methods of Extraction Composition and Stability of Vitamin A and Other Components in Dogfish (*Squalus acanthias*) Liver Oil. *Food Chemistry*, 55(3), 215-220.
- Iglesias S. P. (2014). Handbook of the Marine Fishes of Europe and Adjacent Waters (A natural Classification Based on Collection Specimens, with DNA Barcodes and Standardized Photographs) (Vol. 1) (Chondrichthyans and Cyclostomata). <http://iccanam.mnhn.fr/>.
- Irianto, H. E. (2022). Marine Chondroitin Sulfate and Its Potential Applications. *In Marine Biochemistry* (pp. 247-269). CRC Press.
- Isaacs, R. B., Hellberg, R. S. (2021). Shark Cartilage Supplement Labeling Practices and Compliance with US Regulations. *Journal of Dietary Supplements*, 18(1), 44-56.
- İlkyaz, A. T., Metin, G., Soykan, O., Kınacıgil, H. T. (2008). Length-Weight Relationship of 62 Fish Species from the Central Aegean Sea, Turkey. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 24(6), 699-702.
- İşmen, A. (2003). Age, Growth, Reproduction and Food of Common Stingray (*Dasyatis pastinaca* L., 1758) in Iskenderun Bay, the Eastern Mediterranean. *Fisheries Research*, 60(1), 169-176.
- İşmen, A., Özen, O., Altınağaç, U., Özekinci, U., Ayaz, A. (2007a). Weight-Length Relationships of 63 Fish Species in Saros Bay, Turkey. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 23(6), 707-708.
- İşmen, A., Yiğın, C., İşmen, P. (2007b). Age, Growth, Reproductive Biology and Feed of the Common Guitarfish (*Rhinobatos rhinobatos* Linnaeus, 1758) in Iskenderun Bay, the Eastern Mediterranean Sea. *Fisheries Research*, 84(2), 263-269.

- İşmen, A., Yiğın, C. Ç., Altınağac, U., Ayaz, A. (2009). Length–Weight Relationships for Ten Shark Species from Saros Bay (North Aegean Sea). *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 25, 109-112.
- İşmen, A., Yiğın, C. Ç., İhsanoğlu, M. A., Daban, B. (2018). Length-Weight Relationships for Three Elasmobranch Species from the Sea of Marmara. *Journal of Black Sea/Mediterranean Environment*, 24, 65-73.
- Kabasakal, H. (2021). A Review of Shark Biodiversity in Turkish Waters: Updated Inventory, New Arrivals, Questionable Species, and Conservation Issues. *Annales: Series Historia Naturalis*, 31(2), 181-194.
- Kabasakal, H., Özbek, E.Ö. (2022). Length-Weight Relation of the Angular Rough Shark, *Oxynotus centrina* (Linnaeus,1758) in the Mediterranean Sea. *Natural and Engineering Sciences*, 7(2), 97-107.
- Kabasakal, H., Uzer, U., Gönülal, O., Karakulak, F.S. (2024). Bioecological Lessons Learned from the Neonate Longnose Spurdogs *Squalus blainville* (Squaliformes: Squalidae) Suggest a Potential Nursery Ground in the Marmara Sea. *Acta Adriatica*, 65, 1-14.
- Kara, A., Sağlam, C., Acarlı, D., Cengiz, Ö. (2018). Length-Weight Relationships for 48 Fish Species of the Gediz Estuary, in Izmir Bay (Central Aegean Sea, Turkey). *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 98(4), 879-884.
- Karadurmuş, U. (2022). Length–Weight Relationship and Condition Factor of Sixteen Demersal Fish Species from the Southern Part of the Marmara Sea, Turkey. *Journal of Ichthyology*, 62(4), 543-551.
- Karakulak, F. S., Erk, H., Bilgin, B. (2006). Length–Weight Relationships for 47 Coastal Fish Species from the Northern Aegean Sea, Turkey. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 22(4), 274-278.
- Kasapoğlu, N., Düzgüneş, E. (2013). Length-Weight Relationships of Marine Species Caught by Five Gears from the Black Sea. *Mediterranean Marine Science*, 15(1), 95-100.
- Kaya, G., Başusta, N. (2016). A Study on Age and Growth of Juvenile and Semi Adult *Torpedo nobiliana* Bonaparte, 1835 Inhabiting Iskenderun Bay, Northeastern Mediterranean Sea. *Acta Biologica Turcica*, 29(4), 143-149.
- Lamas, D. L., Massa, A. E. (2024). Narrownose Smoothhound (*Mustelus schmitti*) Shark Liver: From a Residue to a High Added Value Biocompounds. *Food Chemistry Advances*, 4, 100623.
- Li, W., Ura, K., Takagi, Y. (2022). Industrial Application of Fish Cartilaginous Tissues. *Current Research in Food Science*, 5, 698-709.
- Lu, W. C., Chiu, C. S., Chan, Y. J., Guo, T. P., Lin, C. C., Wang, P. C., Lin, P. Y., Mulio, A. T., Li, P. H. (2022). An In Vivo Study to Evaluate the Efficacy of Blue Shark (*Prionace glauca*) Cartilage Collagen as a Cosmetic. *Marine Drugs*, 20(10), 633.
- Merly, L., Smith, S. L. (2015). Pro-Inflammatory Properties of Shark Cartilage Supplement. *Immunopharmacology and Immunotoxicology*, 37(2), 140-147.
- Musick, J. A. (2005). Shark Utilization. In Management Techniques for Elasmobranch Fisheries (pp. 243-251). VIMS Books and Book Chapters.
- Nelson, J. S., Grande, T. C., Wilson, M. V. H. (2016). Fishes of the World (5th ed). John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Official Gazette, (2020). Communiqué No. 5/1 on the Regulation of Commercial Fishing of Aquatic Products, Issue 31221. Available at: <https://www.resmigazete.gov.tr/eskiler/2020/08/20200822-8.pdf> (07.07.24).

- Oğuz, T., Latun, V. S., Latif, M. A., Vladimirov, V. V., Sur, H. I., Markov, A. A., Özsoy, E., Kotovshchikov, B. B., Eremeev, V. V., Ünlüata, Ü. (1993). Circulation in the Surface and Intermediate Layers of the Black Sea. *Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceanographic Research Papers*, 40(8), 1597-1612.
- Onay, H., Dalgıç, G. (2021). Length-Weight Relationships for Fourteen Fish Species Collected by Bottom Trawl from the Eastern Black Sea Coast, Turkey. *Marine Science and Technology Bulletin*, 10(4), 326-332.
- Otero, M., Serena, F., Gerovasileiou, V., Barone, M., Bo, M., Arcos, J. M., Vulcano, A., Xavier, J. (2019). Identification Guide of Vulnerable Species Incidentally Caught in Mediterranean Fisheries. IUCN.
- Özaydın, O., Uçkun, D., Akalın, S., Leblebici, S., Tosunoğlu, Z. (2007). Length-Weight Relationships of Fishes Captured from Izmir Bay, Central Aegean Sea. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 23(6), 695-696.
- Özbek, E. Ö., Çardak, M., Kebapçioğlu, T. (2015). Spatio-Temporal Patterns of Abundance, Biomass and Length-Weight Relationships of *Dasyatis* Species (Pisces: Dasyatidae) in the Gulf of Antalya, Turkey (Levantine Sea). *Journal of Black Sea/Mediterranean Environment*, 21(2), 169-190.
- Özbek, E. Ö., Çardak, M., Kebapçioğlu, T. (2016). Spatio-Temporal Patterns of Abundance, Biomass and Length-Weight Relationships of *Gymnura altavela* (Linnaeus, 1758)(Pisces: Gymnuridae) in the Gulf of Antalya, Turkey (Levantine Sea). *Journal of the Black Sea/Mediterranean Environment*, 22(1), 16-34.
- Özcan, E. İ., Başusta, N. (2018a). Preliminary Study on Age, Growth and Reproduction of *Mustelus mustelus* (Elasmobranchii: Carcharhiniformes: Triakidae) Inhabiting the Gulf of Iskenderun, North-eastern Mediterranean Sea. *Acta Ichthyologica et Piscatoria*, 48(1), 27-36.
- Özcan, E. İ., Başusta, N. (2018b). Some Population Parameters of *Scyliorhinus canicula* (Linnaeus, 1758) from the Northeastern Mediterranean Sea. *Journal of Black Sea/Mediterranean Environment*, 24(1), 51-64.
- Özdemir S., Duyar H. A. (2013). Length-Weight Relationships for Ten Fish Species Collected by Trawl Surveys from Black Sea Coast, Turkey. *International Journal of Chemical, Environmental and Biological Sciences*, 1, 405-407.
- Özdemir, S. (2017). Seasonal Catch Compositions of Turbot Gillnets in Southern Central Black Sea Coasts. *Aquaculture Studies*, 17(4), 325-334.
- Özdemir, S., Büyükdeveci, F., Özsandıkçı, U., Erdem, Y. (2020). Four Important Poisonous Fishes in the Black Sea Coasts: Some Biological Features and Length-weight Relationships. *Journal of New Results in Science*, 9(3), 16-24.
- Özdemir, S., Özsandıkçı, U., Büyükdeveci, F., Erdem, Y. (2021). Seasonal Variations in the Length-Weight Relationships of the Thornback Ray *Raja clavata* L., 1758 (Chondrichthyes: Rajidae) from the Turkish Black Sea Coast. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica*, 73(3), 417-423.
- Özdemir, S., Özsandıkçı, U., Duyar, H. A. (2023). Some Population Parameters of Picked Dogfish (*Squalus acanthias* L. 1758) Incidentally Captured in Commercial Fisheries in Southern Black Sea Shores and a First Record of Angular Roughshark (*Oxynotus centrina*, L. 1758) for Black Sea. *Marine Science and Technology Bulletin*, 12(4), 483-494.

- Öztekin, A., Özekinci, U., Daban, İ. B. (2016). Length-Weight Relationships of 26 Fish Species Caught by Longline from the Gallipoli Peninsula, Turkey (Northern Aegean Sea). *Cahiers de Biologie Marine*, 57(4), 335-342.
- Özten, S., Yiğın, C. Ç., İşmen, A., Cabbar, K. (2024). Biological Assessment of Common Eagle Ray, *Myliobatis aquila* (Linnaeus, 1758) from the Northeastern Mediterranean (Saros Bay), Turkey. *Acta Biologica Turcica*, 37(4), S4:1-12.
- Öztürk, B. (2009). Marine Protected Areas in the High Seas of the Aegean and Eastern Mediterranean Seas, Some Proposals. *Journal of Black Sea/Mediterranean Environment*, 15(1), 69-82.
- Özütemiz, Ş., Kaya, M., Özaydın, O. (2009). Growth and Feeding Characteristics of Two Sharks Species [*Galeus melastomus* Rafinesque, 1810 and *Squalus blainvillei* (Risso, 1826)] from Sığacık Bay (Aegean Sea). *Ege Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 26(3), 211-217.
- Saygu, İ. (2011) Determination of By-catch Rays and Their Survival Rates Caught by Demersal Trawl Fishery in Antalya Bay. Akdeniz University, Institute of Science. Antalya, p 92.
- Seixas, M. J., Martins, E., Reis, R. L., Silva, T. H. (2020). Extraction and Characterization of Collagen from Elasmobranch Byproducts for Potential Biomaterial Use. *Marine Drugs*, 18(12), 617.
- Serena, F., Abella, A. J., Bargnesi, F., Barone, M., Colloca, F., Ferretti, F., Fiorentino, F., Jenrette, J., Moro, S. (2020). Species Diversity, Taxonomy and Distribution of Chondrichthyes in the Mediterranean and Black Sea. *The European Zoological Journal*, 87(1), 497-536.
- Soykan, O., Kınacıgil, H. T. (2021). Length-Weight Relationship of Some Discarded Fish Species with Emphasis on Length at Maturity from the Central Aegean Sea, Turkey. *Thalassas: An International Journal of Marine Sciences*, 37(2), 505-511.
- Şen, Y., Özekinci, U. (2024). Estimation of Economic Losses in Trammel Nets Fisheries Using the Length-Weight Relationship. *Thalassas: An International Journal of Marine Sciences*, 40, 827-834.
- Tanna, P. D., Fofandi, D. C., Motivarash, Y. B. (2020). Processing and Utilization of Shark Cartilage. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*, 8(1), 614-615.
- Taylan, B., Bayhan, B., Sağlam, C., Babaoğlu, A. Ö., Kara, A. (2022). The Length-Weight Characteristics of Five Elasmobranch Species (Pisces: Chondrichthyes) from Izmir Bay (Aegean Sea coast of Turkey): Spring 2018. *Turkish Journal of Agriculture-Food Science and Technology*, 10(2), 368-373.
- Tesch, F. W. (1971). Age and Growth. In *Methods for Assessment of Fish Production in Fresh Waters* (pp. 98-130). Blackwell Scientific Publications.
- Torcu-Koç, H., Erdoğan, Z. (2018). Length-Weight Relationships, Reproduction, Hepatosomatic Index of the Lesser Spotted Catshark, *Scyliorhinus canicula* [L.] the Sea of Marmara, Turkey. *Journal of Balıkesir University Institute of Science and Technology*, 20(2), 98-108.
- Tüney-Kızılkaya, I., Bengil, E. G. T. (2022). Identification Complexity of Critically Endangered *Squatina squatina* (Linnaeus, 1758) and *Squatina aculeata* Cuvier, 1829 in the Mediterranean Sea (Turkey). *Journal of Wildlife and Biodiversity*, 6(4), 9-27.
- Turan, C. (2008). Molecular Systematic Analyses of Mediterranean Skates (Rajiformes). *Turkish Journal of Zoology*, 32(4), 437-442.
- Turan, C., Ergüden, D. (2012). İskenderun Körfezi'nde Nesli Tehlike Altında Olan Kıkırdaklı Balık Türleri. In: *Book of Proceedings. Sualtı Bilim ve Teknolojisi Toplantısı*, 17-18 November 2012, Istanbul, Türkiye, pp. 179-187. [In Turkish].

- Turan, C., Gürlek, M., Başusta, N., Uyan, A., Doğdu, S. A., Karan, S. (2018). A Checklist of the Non-Indigenous Fishes in Turkish Marine Waters. *Natural and Engineering Sciences*, 3(3), 333-358.
- Turan, C., Gürlek, M., Ergüden, D., Kabasakal, H. (2021). A new record for the shark fauna of the Mediterranean Sea: Whale shark, *Rhincodon typus* (Orectolobiformes: Rhincodontidae). *Annales: Series Historia Naturalis*, 31(2), 167-172.
- Turan, C., Ergüden, D., Gürlek, M., Doğdu, S. (2024a). Checklist of Alien Fish Species in the Turkish Marine Ichthyofauna for Science and Policy Support. *Tethys Environmental Science*, 1(2), 50-86.
- Turan, C., Uyan, A., Doğdu, S., Ergüden, D. (2024b). First Record of the Blonde Ray *Raja brachyura* (Rajidae) on Turkish Coasts. *Tethys Environmental Science*, 1(3), 127-134.
- Turan, C., Doğdu, S., Soldo, A. (2024c). Evidence of Nursery Area and Length-Weight Relationships for Longnose Spurdog *Squalus blainville* in the Northeastern Mediterranean. *Tethys Environmental Science*, 1(4), 200-210.
- Turan, C., Gürlek, M., Doğdu, S. A., Ergüden, D., Uyan, A., Ergenler, A., Başusta, N., Soldo, A. (2024d). Phylogenetic Relationships and Conservation Implications of Shark Species from Turkish Waters. *Annales: Series Historia Naturalis*, 34(1), 27-36.
- Turan, H., Sönmez, G., Kaya, Y. (2007). Fatty Acid Profile and Proximate Composition of the Thornback Ray (*Raja clavata*, L. 1758) from the Sinop Coast in the Black Sea. *Journal of FisheriesSciences.com*, 1(2), 97-103.
- TURKSTAT. (2024). Fishery Statistics. Available at <https://biruni.tuik.gov.tr/medas/?kn=97&locale=tr> (07.07.2024).
- Türker-Çakır, D., Torcu-Koç, H., Zeliha, E. (2006). Some Biological Aspects of the Lesser Spotted Dogfish *Scyliorhinus canicula* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Edremit Bay (the Northern Aegean Sea) Turkey. In *The Proceedings of the Workshop on Mediterranean Cartilaginous Fish with Emphasis on Southern and Eastern Mediterranean* (pp. 17-27). Turkish Marine Research Foundation (TUDAV).
- Türker-Çakır, D., Torcu-Koç, H., Başusta, A., Başusta, N. (2008). Length-Weight Relationships of 24 Fish Species from Edremit Bay Aegean Sea. *Ecological Life Sciences*, 3(1), 47-51.
- Türker, D., Zengin, K., Tunay, Ö. K. (2019). Length-Weight Relationships for Nine Chondrichthyes Fish Species from Edremit Bay (North Aegean Sea). *Turkish Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 19(1), 71-79.
- UNEP/MAP SPA/RAC. (2018). Manuel de Formation sur les Poissons Cartilagineux, Identifier et Reconnaître les Raies et Requins de Méditerranée. SPA/RAC & ASCOB-Syrtis.
- Uyan, A., Turan, C., Erdoğan-Eliuz, E. A., Sangün, M. K. (2020a). Antimicrobial Properties of Bioactive Compounds Isolated from Epidermal Mucus in two Ray Species (*Dasyatis marmorata* and *Gymnura altavela*). *Tropical Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 19(10), 2115-2121.
- Uyan, A., Turan, C., Gürlek, M., Yağlıoğlu, D. (2020b). Genetic and Bio-Ecologic Characteristics of Common Pandora *Pagellus erythrinus* from the Eastern Mediterranean Coast of Turkey for the Ecosystem-based Fishery Management. *Genetics of Aquatic Organisms*, 4(1), 29-37.
- Uyan, A., Turan, C., Erdoğan, E. A., Sangün, M. K. (2021). Biochemical Compounds and Their Antimicrobial Activities in Epidermal Mucus Obtained from Two Ray Species *Dasyatis pastinaca* and *Raja miraletus*. *Cahiers de Biologie Marine*, 62(4), 321-330.

- Uyan, A. (2024). Length-Weight Relationships and Growth Parameters of Axillary Seabream *Pagellus acarne* (Risso, 1827) from the Didim Coast in the Southern Aegean Sea. *Aquatic Research*, 7(3), 121-130.
- Uyan, A., Turan C. (2024). Estimation of Growth and Mortality Parameters for the Annular Seabream *Diplodus annularis* (Linnaeus, 1978) in the Southern Aegean Sea. *Turkish Journal of Agriculture-Food Science and Technology*, 12(10), 1796-1805.
- Uyan, A., Turan, C., Doğdu, S. A., Gürlek, M., Yağlıoğlu, D., Sönmez, B. (2024). Genetic and Some Bio-Ecological Characteristics of Lessepsian Lizardfish *Saurida lessepsianus* from the Northeastern Mediterranean Sea. *Tethys Environmental Sciences*, 1(1), 1-16.
- Vazquez, J. A., Fraguas, J., González, P., Serra, J., Valcarcel, J. (2020). Optimal Recovery of Valuable Biomaterials, Chondroitin Sulfate and Bioapatites, from Central Skeleton Wastes of Blue Shark. *Polymers*, 12(11), 2613.
- Vazquez, J. A., Rodriguez-Amado, I., Montemayor, M. I., Fraguas, J., del Pilar Gonzalez, M., Murado, M. A. (2013). Chondroitin Sulfate, Hyaluronic Acid and Chitin/Chitosan Production Using Marine Waste Sources: Characteristics, Applications and Eco-Friendly Processes: A Review. *Marine Drugs*, 11(3), 747-774.
- Vennila, R., Kumar, K. R., Kanchana, S., Arumugam, M., Vijayalakshmi, S., Balasubramaniam, T. (2011). Preliminary Investigation on Antimicrobial and Proteolytic Property of the Epidermal Mucus Secretion of Marine Stingrays. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine*, 1, 239-243.
- Venugopal, V., Kumaran, A. K., Sekhar Chatterjee, N., Kumar, S., Kavilakath, S., Nair, J. R., Mathew, S. (2016). Biochemical Characterization of Liver Oil of *Echinorhinus brucus* (Bramble Shark) and Its Cytotoxic Evaluation on Neuroblastoma Cell Lines (SHSY-5Y). *Scientifica*, 2016(1), 6294030.
- Volpi, N. (2009). Quality of Different Chondroitin Sulfate Preparations in relation to Their Therapeutic Activity. *Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, 61(10), 1271-1280.
- Walker, P., Cavanagh, R. D., Ducrocq, M., Fowler, S. L. (2005). Chapter 7–Regional Overviews: Northeast Atlantic (Including Mediterranean and Black Sea). In *Sharks, Rays and Chimaeras: The Status of the Chondrichthyan Fishes* (pp. 71-95). IUCN.
- Yağlıoğlu, D., Deniz, T., Gürlek, M., Ergüden, D., Turan, C. (2015). Elasmobranch Bycatch in a Bottom Trawl Fishery in the Iskenderun Bay, Northeastern Mediterranean. *Cahiers de Biologie Marine*, 56(3), 237-243.
- Yapıcı, S., Karachle, P. K., Filiz, H. (2015). First Length–Weight Relationships of 11 Fish Species in the Aegean Sea. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 31(2), 398-402.
- Yarmaz, A. (2009). Some Biological Properties of Cartilaginous Fish Living in Edremit Bay and Their Vicinity. Balıkesir University, Institute of Science. Balıkesir, p 159.
- Yeldan, H. Avşar, D. (2007). Length–Weight Relationship for Five Elasmobranch Species from the Cilician Basin Shelf Waters (Northeastern Mediterranean). *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 23(6), 713-714.
- Yeldan H., Avşar D. Manaşırılı M. (2008). Some Biological Peculiarities of Thornback Ray, *Raja clavata* (Linnaeus, 1758) in the Northeast Mediterranean. *Ege Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 25(3), 221-228.

- Yeldan, H., Avşar, D., Manaşırlı, M. (2009). Age, Growth and Feeding of the Common Stingray (*Dasyatis pastinaca*, L., 1758) in the Cilician Coastal Basin, Northeastern Mediterranean Sea. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 25, 98-102.
- Yeldan, H. (2018). Estimating Some Population Parameters and Stock Assessment of Spiny Butterfly Ray, *Gymnura altavela* (Linnaeus, 1758) the Levant Basin Coast (Northeastern Mediterranean). *Indian Journal of Animal Research*, 52(12), 1790-1796.
- Yeldan, H., Gündoğdu, S. (2018). Morphometric Relationships and Growth of Common Stingray, *Dasyatis pastinaca* (Linnaeus, 1758) and Marbled Stingray, *Dasyatis marmorata* (Steindachner, 1892) in the Northeastern Levantine Basin. *Journal of the Black Sea/Mediterranean Environment*, 24(1), 10-27.
- Yemişken, E. (2017). Comparison of Trawl Fisheries Effects on Chondrichthyan Species in Fishing Areas of Eastern Mediterranean Sea. Istanbul University, Institute of Science. Istanbul, p 142.
- Yığın, C. Ç., İşmen, A. (2009). Length–Weight Relationships for Seven Rays from Saros Bay (North Aegean Sea). *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 25 (Suppl. 1), 106-108.
- Yığın, C. Ç., İşmen, A. (2010a). Age, Growth, Reproduction and Feed of Longnosed Skate, *Dipturus oxyrinchus* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Saros Bay, the North Aegean Sea. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 26(6), 913-919.
- Yığın, C. Ç., İşmen, A. (2010b). Age, Growth Reproduction and Feed of Bottlenose Skate, *Rostroraja alba* (Lacepede, 1803) in Saros Bay, the North Aegean Sea. In: Proceeding Book. ICES Annual Science Conference 2010, 20-24 September 2010, Nantes, France. p. 25.
- Yığın, C. Ç., İşmen, A. (2012). Age, Growth and Reproduction of the Common Stingray, *Dasyatis pastinaca* from the North Aegean Sea. *Marine Biology Research*, 8(7), 644-653.
- Yığın, C. Ç., İşmen, A. (2014). Age, Growth and Reproduction of the Rough Ray, *Raja radula* (Delaroche, 1809) in Saros Bay (North Aegean Sea). *Journal of Black Sea/Mediterranean Environment*, 20(3), 213-227.
- Yığın, C. Ç., İşmen, A., Önal, U., Arslan, M. (2015). Cartilaginous Fishes and Fisheries in the Aegean Sea. In *The Aegean Sea Marine Biodiversity, Fisheries, Conservation and Governance* (pp. 286-302). Turkish Marine Research Foundation (TUDAV).
- Yığın, C. Ç., İşmen, A. (2016). Age and Growth of Spiny Dogfish *Squalus acanthias* (Squalidae: Chondrichthyes) in the North Aegean Sea. *Pakistan Journal of Zoology*, 48(4), 1185-1191.
- Yığın, C. Ç., Çakır, F., Cabbar, K., Kızılkaya, B., Ormancı, H. B., Öztekin, A., Özüdoğru, Y. (2019). The Liver Lipid Fatty Acid Composition of Two Cartilaginous Fish, the Thornback Ray (*Raja clavata*) and the Common Smooth-Hound (*Mustelus mustelus*). *Aquatic Research*, 2(3), 143-153.
- Yığın, C. Ç., İşmen, A. (2021). Biological Aspects of the Brown Ray (*Raja miraletus* Linnaeus, 1758) in the Saros Bay, the Northern Aegean Sea. *Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University Journal of Marine Sciences and Fisheries*, 4(1), 32-41.
- Yığın, C. Ç., Cabbar, K., İşmen, A., İhsanoğlu, M. A., Daban, İ. B. (2023). Age, Growth and Reproduction of the Thornback ray, *Raja clavata* (Linnaeus, 1758) in the Waters Off Gökçeada (the Northern Aegean Sea). *Thalassas: An International Journal of Marine Sciences*, 39(2), 943-951.
- Zenetos, A., Gofas, S., Verlaque, M., Çınar, M., Garcia-Raso, J., Bianchi, C., Morri, C., Azzurro, E., Bilecenoğlu, M., Frogli, C., Siokou, I., Violanti, D., Sfriso, A., San Martin, G., Giangrande, A., Katağan, T., Ballesteros, E., Ramos-Espla, A., Mastrototaro, F. Ocana, O., Zingone, A.,

Gambi, M., Streftaris, N. (2010). Alien Species in the Mediterranean Sea by 2010. A Contribution to the Application of European Union's Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD). Part I. Spatial Distribution. *Mediterranean Marine Science*, 11(2), 381.